

Open and Distance Education and Inmate's Rehabilitation and Reintegration in Enugu Maximum Special Custodial Centre

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Abstract

The paper examines impact of open and distance education in prisoner's rehabilitation and reintegration in Enugu Maximum Custodial Centre, from 2011 to 2024. The paper adopted a descriptive research design while data were collected through survey (Questionnaires and oral interviews) and documentary sources. The sample size of the study is seventy-six (76) participants, made up of seventy (73) serving and former inmates/students as well as three (3) officials of the Custodial Centre selected using a purposive sampling method. Data collected from questionnaire were presented in tables, figures, percentages and frequencies. Data from interviews and documentary sources were analyzed using content analysis. The quantitative data generated were subjected to inferential statistical tool using multiple regression analysis with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Science (IBM SPSS) Software, version 22.0. The result showed that open and distance learning (ODL) has been effective and efficient in prisoners' rehabilitation and reintegration and that challenges such as lack of adequate structures/classroom building for the program, lack of internet services, and lack of budgetary support, among others, hinder the program. The paper concludes that prisoner education and literacy programs such as ODL should be included in the nation's education curriculum and made compulsory for prison inmates as part of their rehabilitation and reintegration programs.

Keywords: Open and distance learning, prison inmates, prisoners' education, rehabilitation reformation and reintegration, Nigeria correctional service

Introduction

One of the reformatory programs recently introduced in the Prisoners' Rehabilitation, Reformation and Reintegration in Nigeria Correctional Service, formerly known as the Nigeria Prison Services, is the opening of National Open University of Nigeria Special Study Centers in some custodial centers across the country to help inmates there acquire education. One of the problems confronting prisoner's rehabilitation, reformation, and reintegration in Nigeria is how to equip inmates with the needed skills that will enable them to earn a living after serving their jail terms or after being discharged by the courts in the case of awaiting trial inmates. The majority of the inmates in prisons in Nigeria do not have good education prior to their incarceration, and the Enugu Maximum Custodial Centre, formally referred to as Enugu Maximum Security Prisons, is one of the prison facilities confronted with the problem. Despite the fact that majority of the prison inmates in the correctional centers such as the Enugu Maximum Custodial Centre are at their active age of between 17 and 50 years, an age bracket that, according to Ogidan (2008) cited in Ajufu

(2013), is a period of life when people of that age grade are supposed to be educated and capable of contributing to the economy of their society, Before now, prisoners (those in Enugu Maximum Custodial Centre inclusive) were denied access to functional learning that can be compared to what is happening in the free world. Incarceration accounts for a major reason why prison inmates in Nigeria do not have access to learning because of the problem of location.

One of the reformatory programs recently introduced in the process of prisoners' rehabilitation, reformation and reintegration in Nigerian Correctional Service, formerly known as Nigerian Prison Services, is the opening of National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) Special Study Centres in some Custodial Centres across the country to offer open and distance learning education to qualified inmates. These study centres are located in Enugu, Awka, Port Hacourt, Keffi, Abuja, Sauka, Kuje, Lafia, Kaduna, Umudike, Ilaro, and Kirikiri Prisons. Adeyeye (2019) observes that the purpose of prison education is to improve the skills and knowledge of inmates, which will make them employable by means of formal, technical, and vocational education. This goes further to reduce "recidivism," which refers to the chronic repetition of crime. Ekpenyong and Dudafa (2016) note that prison education through open and distance learning has contributed to the reformation of prison inmates and put them in a position to be able to get employment when they come out of prison, thus helping them to shun any form of criminality and, at the same time, a stepping stone towards their inclusion and reintegration into the society".

The Enugu Maximum Custodial Centre was established in 1915 with a carrying capacity of 638 prison inmates. However, the facility is presently holding over 2000 inmates in custody; made up of awaiting trial and convicted inmates (Iloafonsi, 2023). Open and Distance Education was opened at the Custodial Centre on July 11, 2011 with an initial student intake of 12 inmates who have their WAEC and NECO with a minimum of five credits and who celebrated their first matriculation ceremony. Out of that number, two enrolled to study law, one enrolled to study Christian Theology, another one enrolled to study Agricultural Extension and Management, three enrolled to study Peace Studies and Conflict Resolution, and another one enrolled to study Mathematics and Computer Science, while the remaining four inmates enrolled to study Information and Communication Technology. The National Open University of Nigeria, the institution that started Open and Distance Education at the Custodial Centre, placed all the inmates on a 50% subsidy and later on a 100% subsidy on all registration payments, which included course registrations, tuition fees, examination fees, among others, while the Nigerian Correctional Service and Isaac Blessing Foundation provided the remaining 50 percent of tuition and other fees for the pioneer students. The churches, as well as some other non-governmental organizations, parents, and relatives of the students/inmates equally provided the students with their own support (Iloafonsi, 2023).

In 2015, one of the inmates graduated with a Bachelor of Science Degree (B.Sc) in Peace Studies and Conflict Resolution and received an award for the best graduating student in all the Special Study Centres in Nigeria with a cumulative grade point average of 4.36. He immediately enrolled in his Master's Degree program. Furthermore, the number of graduates in the study center has increased. When the school started, the Nigeria Correctional Service, formally known as the

Nigeria Prison Service, donated one of the prison cells in the Enugu Custodial Centre as a classroom for the students (Iloafonsi, 2023).

Before the introduction of open and distance learning in the Enugu Maximum Custodial Centre in 2011 by the National Open University of Nigeria, all that the centre had were vocational facilities such as carpentry, tailoring, and welding workshops, while the average educational attainment of the inmates was primary and secondary education provided by the Enugu State Government. Scholars who have written on prisoners' rehabilitation, reformation, and reintegration in Nigeria seldom explore or investigate the educational system in the prison facilities in Nigeria. Some of these scholars focused on the health conditions of prison inmates, lack of infrastructure in prisons, inadequate funding and corruption, as well as recidivism in prisons (Esiri, 2016). This paper seeks to improve on the previous studies by examining Open and Distance Education in Prisoners' Rehabilitation and Reintegration in Enugu Maximum Custodial Centre from its inception in 2011 to 2021.

Objectives of the Study

The specific objectives of the study were to

- a) Find out the effectiveness of open and distance education in prisoners' rehabilitation and reintegration at the Enugu Custodial Centre.
- b) Ascertain how open and distance learning delivery systems impact on prisoners' rehabilitation, reformation, and reintegration.
- c) Discover the challenges confronting prisoners' rehabilitation, reformation, and reintegration with open and distance education at Enugu Maximum Custodial Centre.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated for the study:

1. How does the introduction of the open and distance learning program at the Enugu Custodial Centre contribute to prisoners' rehabilitation and reintegration?
2. How does the open and distance learning delivery systems impact on prisoners' rehabilitation, reformation, and reintegration?
3. What are the challenges confronting prisoners' rehabilitation, reformation, and reintegration with open and distance education at Enugu Maximum Custodial Centre?

Hypothesis

The study proposed the following hypotheses:

Ho¹: there is a significant effect of open and distance education on prisoners' reformation, rehabilitation and reintegration at Enugu Custodial Centre.

Ho¹: provision of administrative facilities and infrastructural support have significant influence on prisoner adaptation to open and distance learning programme in the Enugu Custodian Centre

Ho³: Institutional challenges, inadequate study facilities, and personal challenges have significant effects on prisoners' reformation, rehabilitation, and reintegration with and Distance Education at Enugu Custodial Centre

Review of Related Literature

Nigerian Correctional Service

The Nigerian Correctional Service, formerly known as the Nigerian Prison Service, started in 1861 when Western Modeled Prisons were established in the country by the British Colonialists. As at 1910, prison facilities were established in Degema, Calabar, Onitsha, Benin, Ibadan, Sapele, Jebba, and Lokoja (Orakwe&Chigbogu, 2016). The first officer in charge of prisons in Nigeria was Colonel V. L. Mabb, who was appointed Director of Prison Services by the then Governor General, Sir Donald Cameron. In 1972, the Federal Military Government enacted Decree No. 9, which made clear the goal of the Nigerian Prison Service (Orakwe & Chigbogu, 2016). According to Adetula et al. (2010), the decree empowers it to: Keep convicted offenders (prisoners) for safe custody; keep awaiting trial inmates in custody, until the law courts ask for their production; punish offenders as instructed by the law courts; reform the convicted prisoners and rehabilitate and re-integrate prisoners who have completed their sentences in the prison.

Open and Distance Education (ODL)

Open and distance education is described as a combination of approaches that open opportunities for education and that frees learners from the problems of time and place as individuals and groups are offered flexible learning opportunities (Moore & Tait, 2002, cited in Ofole (2015). Furthermore, Ofole (2015) draws a distinction between open and distance learning and conventional educational delivery and states that in open and distance learning there are no "structured face-to-face contacts between the students and the teachers, unlike in the conventional educational system." He also maintains that ODL presents "high quality, self-directed, learner-centered printed instructional materials that are made available to students."

Prisoners' Rehabilitation, Reformation, and Reintegration

Ugwuoke and Ameh (2014) define prisoners' rehabilitation as "the reforming of the personality and behaviour of someone convicted of committing an offence through the process of educational and/or therapeutic treatment, to enable him or her to go back to society and be accepted by such society." Asokhia and Agbonluae (2013) note that "effective rehabilitation program in prisons could assist inmates acquire suitable skills, prospect development, attitudinal and behavioral changes, and for this reason, the programs are helpful to prison inmates for the promotion of their potentials, such as physical, mental-health, psychological, social, vocational, and economic potentials. On the other hand, the program gives them the opportunity to use skills acquired from rehabilitation to live meaningful lives in society." Nwune *et al.* (2019) studied the perception of rehabilitation, reformation, and reintegration programs in Anambra State Prison Command and observed that "there is a mixed perception about the functionality of rehabilitation program among the prison community because inmates tend to perceive rehabilitation program as less functional, but on the contrary, prison officials perceive them to be fairly functional." They also identified that insufficient funding, and government hypocrisy are among the factors affecting rehabilitation. Ogbaka et al. (2017) define prisoners' reformation as the process of being rescued from error and returning to a rightful course or changing from a sinful to a normal life.

What this means, according to them, is that the reformation of prison inmates entails changing them from a sinful life to a normal life. Nkwocha *et al.* (2017) state that reformation means making the offender better by trying to modify his or her delinquent behaviors and making him/her refrain from those criminal behaviors. The United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODOC, 2020) states that prison reformation programs involve the use of educational programs, vocational training, and skill acquisition to train a prisoner to have the capacity to live as a law-abiding citizen whenever he or she is released. Prisoner reintegration refers to the reentry of prison inmates back into society after their incarceration. Reintegration occurs after the prisoner regains freedom (Bryce, 2020). On the importance of rehabilitation of prisoners, the United Nation Office for Drugs and Crime (UNODOC, 2018) notes that most inmates are faced with social adaptation issues such as stigmatization and ostracism from their family and their community, as well as their inability to secure housing or return to formal education, among others, and unless they are helped to overcome these issues, they risk social rejection, recommitting offenses and thus going back to prison. UNODOC (2018) states further that rehabilitation of prisoners and their reintegration into society should be among the major objectives of every criminal justice system.

Prisoner Education

Education means any process – whether in schools, or informal or non-formal settings – that develops in children or adults the knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values leading to behavior change (Bolarinwa et al., 2006, cited in Adenyi, 2016). Sutton (1993), cited in Igbinovia and Omorogiuwa (2019) note that educational programs in prisons assist in keeping inmates busy, modify their attitudes, and put them in a position to be gainfully employed whenever they leave prison. Prison education is part of the prison reform movement. It can open up opportunities, enlighten prison inmates, broaden their horizons and build their self-confidence, which has been depleted by incarceration. Vandalla (2019) argues that the mandate to provide "correctional education" to those in prisons originated from the United Nations Declarations, Conventions, and Standards such as the Universal Declaration of Human Rights of 1948, the United Nation Standard Minimum Rules for Treatment of Prisoners of 1955, and the Mandela Rules 2015 and that a lot of countries have been using education for their prisoners' rehabilitation program targeted toward changing them from a law-breaker to a law abiding and productive citizen when released.

The introduction of education to prison inmates is not new. According to Jovanic (2011), the focus of the first congress of the International Commission on Criminal Justice and Penal Institutions, held in London in 1872, was on the issue of the education of inmates. Kalu (2002), cited in Ogbaka (2017), states that the evolution of prison education in Nigeria's prisons can be traced to Mr. R.H. Dolan, who, in 1946, as the Colonial Director in charge of prisons in the country, introduced a vocational education program in prison facilities in the country, with an emphasis on training the inmates in various skills and trades.

Theoretical Framework

The paper adopted the Good Lives Model and Jean Hampton Rehabilitation Theory to explain the importance of education in prisoner rehabilitation and reintegration

Good Life Model

The Good Lives Model (GLM) of offenders' was developed by Tony Ward in 2002. The assumption of the theory is that the knowledge and skills a prisoner acquires through education and training programs may promote his or her self-sufficiency upon release. According to the theorists, GLM presumes that offenders, like all humans, value certain states of mind, personal characteristics, and experiences that are described as primary goods. Willis et al. (2013) add that the theory focuses on giving assistance to offenders through the process of "development and implementation of programs which help them to desist from crime." Ward & Gannon (2006) note that the GLM perspective indicates that rehabilitation programs should not be implemented in an environment where human rights are not respected, an indication that prisoners' education is a human rights matter for prison inmates.

Jean Hampton, Rehabilitation Theory

The theory was propounded by Jean Hampton in 1984 in his paper titled "*The Moral Education Theory of Punishment*." The tenet of the theory, according to Ugwuoke and Ameh (2014), is that "people are not natively criminals and that it is possible to restore a criminal to a useful life—to a life in which they contribute positively to the development of themselves and society." Furthermore, Mohd *et al.* (2013) note that the theory as applied to prisoners' rehabilitation matters focuses on individual rehabilitation, which takes into account education for prisoners, their societal integration, and rehabilitation of their criminal mentality. Nwune *et al.* (2019) posit that the theory seeks to decrease recidivism because it assumes that rehabilitation program for prison inmates will help them to live purposeful lives after completing their jail term. It also supports the belief and idea that an offender can be saved not only with punishment but also by recognizing the social inequalities and circumstances that could lead one to criminality. The application of the Good Lives Model (GLM) of the offenders here is to explain how relevant knowledge and skills a prisoner acquires through education and training program during incarceration can make him or her self-sustained upon release. Similarly, Jean Hampton's Rehabilitation Theory is to explain that for inmates' rehabilitation intervention program at Enugu Maximum Custodial Centers to be successful, such program should be targeted towards making the prisoners live a purposeful life after discharge.

Methodology

The population of the study is composed of 73 inmates and 3 senior officials of the Nigerian Correctional Services (NCS), bringing the total sample size to seventy-six (76). The participants were selected through a purposive sampling technique based on their knowledge of the topic of the study. The study adopted the survey and documentary methods of data collection. Survey data was collected through a structured questionnaire and oral interviews, while documentary data was collected from data already in existing documents of both the Nigeria Correctional Service Enugu State Command and the National Open University of Nigeria.

Furthermore, the 3 officials of the Nigerian Correctional Service interviewed were the Controller of Correctional Service Enugu State Command, the officer in-charge of After Care Services in the Custodial Centre, who is also the Desk Officer in-charge of National Open University of Nigeria's

Open and Distance Learning Program in the Custodial Centre, and the Assistant Desk Officer participated in the interview. Data collected from questionnaire were presented in tables, figures, percentages and frequencies. The quantitative data generated were subjected to inferential statistical tool using multiple regression analysis with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Science (IBM SPSS) Software, version 22.0 while Data from interviews and documentary sources were analyzed using content analysis

Result and Discussion

Table 1: The number of inmates that have graduated through the Open and Distance Learning program of National Open University of Nigeria at Enugu Custodial Centre’s Special Study Centre and their course of study

Department	Frequency	Percentage
Peace Studies and Conflict resolution	21	28.7
Law	3	4.1
Mathematics and Computer Science	2	2.7
Entrepreneurship and Business Management	12	16.4
Business Administration	2	2.7
Theology	1	1.4
Political Science	5	6.8
Criminology and Security Studies	6	8.2
Computer Science	1	1.4
Public Administration	3	4.1
Agricultural Extension and Management	1	1.4
Economics	2	2.7
Accounting	1	1.4
Information Technology	1	1.4
Those at the concluding stage of their studies in various departments.	12	16.4
Total	73	99.8 (100%)

Source: Enugu Custodial Special Study Centre Students Records (2024)

Table 2: Degrees obtained by inmates through ODL at Enugu Custodial Centre

Degrees	Frequency	Percentage
B.Sc	52	71.2
M.Sc	6	8.2
MBA	2	2.7
PGD	1	1.4
Those at the concluding stage of their studies in various departments.	12	16.4
Total	73	99.9

Source: Enugu Custodial Special Study Centre Students Records (2024)

Effectiveness of open and distance education in prisoners' rehabilitation and reintegration at the Enugu Custodial Centre

Table 3: showed Respondent's response on how often they have facilitators/lectures with their facilitator (tutors).

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Very Often	3	4.1
Often	4	5.5
Not often	9	12.3
Not at all	57	78.1
Total	73	100

On the frequency of facilitation/lectures with their facilitators (tutors), 3 respondents (4.1%) responded that they do have facilitation/lectures with their facilitators (tutors) very often, 3 respondents (5.5%) responded that they have it often, 9 respondents (12.3%) responded that they do have facilitation /lecture but not often while majority of them numbering 57 (78.1%) responded that they do not have facilitation/lectures at all in Enugu Custodial Centre.

Table 4: Respondents response on how they source of their study materials.

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Through parents	16	21.9
The churches	23	31.5
Non-Governmental Organizations	9	12.3
Internet	3	4.1
Correctional Service Authority	7	9.6
Friends	5	6.8
Relatives	10	13.7
Total	73	99.9 or 100

On the sources of study materials the study found that 16 of the respondents (21.9%) sourced their study materials through their parents, 23(31.5%) sourced the materials through the churches, 9 respondents(12.3%) sourced their study materials through non-governmental organizations, 10(13.7%) responded that they sourced the materials from internet through prison officials, 5(6.8%) sourced them from friends while the remaining 10 respondents (13.7%) responded that they sourced their study materials through relatives.

Table 5: Respondent's response on the efficiency of open and distance learning as a means of rehabilitation and reintegration.

Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Very efficient	55	75.3
Efficient	14	19.2
Not efficient	4	5.5
Very bad	0	0
Total	73	100

On the efficiency of Open and Distance Learning as a means of Rehabilitation and Reintegration, 55 respondents (75.3%) responded that Open and Distance Learning is very effective means of rehabilitation and reintegration, 14 respondents (19.2%) responded that it is effective, 4 (5.5%) responded that it is not effective. Supporting the above responses, the Desk Officer of National Open University of Nigeria, Enugu Custodial Special Study Centre during interview agreed with the respondents and stated that ODL has been very effective means of rehabilitation and reintegration of prison inmates.

Test of Hypothesis One.

Ho¹: there is a significant effect of open and distance education on prisoners’ reformation, rehabilitation and reintegration at Enugu correctional centre.

Table 6: Multiple regression analysis of significant effect of open and distance education on prisoners’ reformation, rehabilitation, and reintegration.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	R Std. Error of the F Estimate	Sig.	
1	.534 ^a	.285	.281	.538	69.496	.000 ^b

a. Predictors: Open and distance Education

In table 1, multiple regression analysis was conducted to assess the effect of open and distance education on prisoners’ reformation, rehabilitation, and reintegration at Enugu correctional centre. The result showed that correlation coefficient of .534 indicated open and distance education is positively related to prisoners’ reformation, rehabilitation, and reintegration. The R² coefficient of .285 indicated that 28% variation in prisoners’ reformation, rehabilitation, and reintegration is attributed to effectiveness of open and distance education. The F-value of 69.496 with associated p-value (sig.) of .000 indicated that open and distance education had a significant effect on prisoners’ reformation, rehabilitation, and reintegration at Enugu correctional centre. Therefore the alternative hypothesis is accepted.

Impact of Open and distance learning delivery systems on prisoners’ rehabilitation, reformation, and reintegration.

Table 7: Respondent’s response on the impacts of Open and Distance Education in prisoners’ rehabilitation and reintegration in Enugu Custodial Centre

Variables	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Do you agree that studying through Open and Distance Learning (ODL) has improved your skill and capacity?	55 75.3%	14 19.2%	4 5.5%	0 0%
Do you agree that ODL has given you the capacity to live a crime free life?	42 57.6%	22 30.1%	6 8.2	3 4.1
The education you received through ODL will help you to have strong	19 26%	34 46.6%	13	7 9.6
			17.8	

	connection with your family and community.				
	The certificates you received from ODL in Enugu Custodial Centre will help to contribute meaningfully to the society?	27 37%	46 63%	0 %	0 %
	Do you agree that academic discipline will make you to be self-reliant after jail?	51 69.9%	16 21.9%	2 2.7%	4 5.5%
	The certificate you got through Open and Distance Learning will make you to be employable do you agree?	30 41.1%	27 37%	9 12.3%	7 9.6%
7	Studying through ODL keeps you busy in Custodial Centre do you agree?	28 38.4	29 39.7	6 8.2	10 13.7

The study found that 42 respondents (57.5%) strongly agreed that studying through Open and Distance Learning (ODL) has modified their characters, 19 respondents (26%) agreed to that, 5(6.8%) disagreed while 7 respondents strongly disagreed. Similarly, 42 respondents (57.5%) strongly agreed that the literacy skills they acquired through ODL is sufficient to discourage them from going back to crime, 22 respondents (30.1%) agreed to that, 6(8.2%) disagreed while 3(4.1%) strongly disagreed that the literacy skills they acquired through ODL is 51 sufficient to discourage them from going back to crime. Those who strongly agreed that ODL has brightened their mind and thinking were 25(34.2%), 31 of them (42.5%) agreed, 9(12.3%) disagreed while the remaining 8(10.9%) strongly disagreed. The study also found that 55 respondents (73.3%) strongly agreed that studying through Open and Distance Learning (ODL) at Enugu Custodial Centre has improved their literacy skills and capacity, 14 respondents (19.2%) agreed, 4(5.5%) disagreed while none strongly disagreed. In a similar manner, 42 respondents (57.6%) strongly agreed that Open and Distance Learning (ODL) has given them the capacity to live a crime free life after jail, 22 (30.1%) agreed, 6(8.2%) disagreed while the remaining 3 respondents (4.1%) disagreed. Those who strongly agreed that education they received through Open and Distance Learning will help them to have strong connection with their families and community were 19(26%), those who agreed were 34(46.6%), those who disagreed were 13(17.8%) while those who strongly disagreed were 7(9.6%). Furthermore, 27 respondents (37%) strongly agreed that the certificates they received from ODL in Enugu Custodial Centre will help them to contribute meaningfully to the society, those who agreed to that were 46(63%) while none disagreed nor strongly disagreed. Those who strongly agreed that their academic discipline will make them to be self-reliant after jail were 51 respondents (69.9%), 16 of them (21.9%) agreed, 2(2.7%) disagreed and those who strongly disagreed were 4(5.5%).

In a similar manner, those who strongly agreed that the certificate they got through Open and Distance Learning will make them to be employable were 30 respondents (41.1%), those who agreed to that were 27(37%), those who disagreed were 9 (12.3%) while those who strongly disagreed were 7 (9.6%). Those who strongly agreed that studying through ODL keeps them busy in the Custodial Centre were 28 respondents (38.4%), those who agreed were 29(39.7%), 6(8.2%) disagreed while 10(13.7%) respondents strongly disagreed

On whether ODL programme has led to behavioral changes on the side of the inmates, one of the interviewee (the Desk Officer) responded that the answer is yes because during their incarceration NOUN provided a platform for them to be busy and being busy reading their study materials and engaging in other academic activities; make them to be well reformed because such opportunity makes them to be high in knowledge and information. So based on the above analysis ODL has changed and modified the behaviour of the inmates/students. On admission into the prison facility, some of the inmates who passed through the programme in the Custodial Center had questionable character before, but the program performed them and they never come back to the Center as an inmate, instead, many of them do come to visit their fellow inmates. In the same manner, the Deputy Desk Officer of NOUN who was also interviewed responded thus: “Well ODL programme has assisted us to reform the inmates and evidence we have is that none of them that enrolled in the programme has been involved in any anti-social behaviour while in incarceration and after discharge. Similarly, none of them have been involved in recidivism which shows that ODL helps to reform them. Under the programme you study at your own pace, some of the inmates on entry into the prison facility here have different background educationally, ODL has helped to complement the reformatory program here.

The results were corroborated during an interview with the Controller Nigerian Correctional Service (CSS) Enugu State Command who stated thus: “Open and Distance Learning in prisons as provided by National Open University of Nigeria has been of immense benefit to the inmates. It has made positive impact in prisoner’s rehabilitation reformation and reintegration. When inmates are exposed to this learning process, they are transformed. It is a program that helps to bring out the best in inmates who otherwise have been presumed to have been lost in the society. Open and Distance Learning is a very crucial aspect of rehabilitation. It is a powerful instrument if properly managed to change the behaviour and attitudes of offenders generally”.

The Desk Officer corroborated the CSS response and added that inmates who graduated in the Centre join those outside prisons in the labour market and this makes them to have a sense of belonging in the society and that ODL program has led to behavioral changes on the side of the inmates, because during their incarceration NOUN provided a platform for them to be busy and being busy reading their study materials and engaging in other academic activities; make them to be well reformed because such opportunity makes them to acquire knowledge that will help them after incarceration.

Effects of infrastructural facilities and administrative support on Open and Distance Learning at Enugu Custodial Centre.

Table 8: Respondents response on the effects of infrastructural facilities and administrative support on Open and Distance Learning at Enugu Custodial Centre.

S/N	Variables	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
	Do you agree the number of computers for ODL in Enugu Custodial Centre is adequate for your study needs?	25 34.2%	18 24.6%	19 26%	11 15%
	Does the provision of modern seats for your studies by National Open University of Nigeria motivates you in your study?	49 67.1%	16 21.9%	2 2.7%	6 8.2%
	Do you agree that free tuition fee from NOUN encouraged you to study in ODL?	52 71.2%	21 28.8%	0 %	0 %
	Were you in agreement that open and free access to your course materials will improve your academic performance?	40 54.8%	23 31.5%	3 4.1%	7 9.6%
	Do you agree or disagree that the current building housing ODL progmmme in the Custodial Centre is adequate for your study	10 13.7%	13 17.8%	32 43.8%	18 24.7%

The study found that that 25 respondents (34.2%) strongly agreed that the number of computers for ODL in Enugu Custodial Centre are adequate for their study needs , 18 (24.6%) agreed to that, 19(26%) disagreed while 11(15%) strongly disagreed. Those who strongly agreed that the provision of modern seats for their studies by National Open University of Nigeria motivate them in their study were 49(67.1%), 16(21.9%) agreed, 2(2.7%) strongly disagreed and the remaining 6(8.2%) strongly disagreed. Furthermore, 52(71.2%) respondents strongly agreed that free tuition fee from NOUN encouraged them to study. Those who strongly agreed that open and free access to their course materials improved their academic performance were 40(54.8%), those who agreed were 23(31.5%), those who disagreed were 3 (4.1%) while those who strongly disagreed were 7 (9.6%).

Similarly, 10 respondents strongly agreed that the current building housing ODL progmmme at Enugu Custodial Centre is adequate for their study, 13(17.8%) agreed to that, 32(43.8%) disagreed, while 18(24.7%) strongly disagreed. Corroborating the above responses from the respondents the Desk Officer of Enugu Custodial Centre during oral interview responded thus: “NOUN has been magnanimous to us; the institution granted inmates tuition free education, they do no pay any

school fees, they provide their instructional materials free of charge. All their registration processes are done free for the inmates. The instructional material they cannot provide, we help and make copies from the ones we have”.

Test of Hypothesis Two

Ho²: provision of administrative facilities and infrastructural support have significant influence on prisoner adaptation to open and distance learning programme in the Enugu Custodian Centre.

Table 9: multiple regression analysis of significant effects of provision of administrative facilities and infrastructural support have significant effects on prisoner adaptation to open and distance learning programme.

Model	Unstandardized		Standardized t	Sig.
	Coefficients			
	B	Std. Error	Beta	
(Constant)	-.370	.171	-2.165	.031
Adequacy of Available Computer	.001	.039	.001	.032
1 Provision of Modern Seat	.138	.045	.120	3.077
Free tuition	.393	.045	.395	8.646
Free access to material	.484	.057	.398	8.550
Current Building Housing	.136	.035	.173	3.911

a. Dependent Variable: prisoner adaptation

In table 2, multiple regression analysis was conducted to assess the effects of provision of administrative facilities and infrastructural support on prisoner adaptation to open and distance learning programme. The t-test result showed that probability values of (adequacy of available Computer, Provision of Modern seat, free tuition, and current building housing) with Beta coefficient of .001, .138, .393, .484, and .136 respectively, positively influenced prisoners’ adaptation to open and distance learning programme. The associated p-values (sig.) were all less than 0.05 level of significance, an indication that these exogenous variables have positive significant influence on prisoners’ adaptation to open and distance learning programme in the Enugu Custodian Centre. Hence, this mean that there is a significant influence of provision of administrative facilities and infrastructural support on prisoner adaptation to open and distance learning programme in the Enugu Custodian Centre. Therefore the alternative hypothesis is accepted.

Challenges hindering open and distance education in prisoners' rehabilitation and reintegration at Enugu Custodial Centre

Table 9: Respondents response on Institutional challenges hindering Open and Distance Education in prisoners' rehabilitation and reintegration at Enugu Custodial Centre.

Variables	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Do you agree that lack of funding affects your rehabilitation with Open and Distance Learning in Enugu Custodial Centre?	55 75.3%	14 19.2%	0 0%	4 5.5%
Do you agree that lack of access to current information hinders your education in ODL?	42 57.5%	18 24.7%	12 16.4%	1 1.4%
Were you in agreement that inadequate study time before lock up does not give you adequate learning space.	28 38.4%	21 28.7%	13 17.8%	11 15%
Does noise in Prison cell distracts you from studying	57 78%	16 22%	0 0%	0 0%
Do you agree that lack of special building for ODL in Enugu Custodial Centre affects your academic performance?	19 26%	46 63%	2 2.7%	6 8.2%
Were in agreement that Custodial Center environment is not conducive for learning?	21 28.8%	23 31.5%	14 19.2%	15 20.5%

Results showed that on institutional challenges hindering Open and Distance Education in prisoners' rehabilitation and reintegration at Enugu Custodial Centre, 55(75.3%) respondents strongly agreed that lack of funding affects their rehabilitation with Open and Distance Learning in Enugu Custodial Centre, 14(19.2%) agreed, none disagreed while 4 (5.5%) strongly disagreed, 42 respondents (57.5%) strongly agreed that lack of access to current information hinder their education in ODL, 18 (24.6%) agreed to that, 12(16.4%) disagreed while 1(1.4%) strongly disagreed. Furthermore, 28 respondents (38.4%) strongly agreed that inadequate study time before lock up does not give them adequate learning space, 21(28.7%) respondents agreed, 13(17.8%) strongly disagreed while 11(15%) disagreed. Those who strongly agreed that noise in Prison cell distracts them from studying were 57 respondents (78%), 16(22%) respondents agreed while none disagreed nor strongly disagreed. Similarly, 19(26%) respondents strongly agreed that lack of special building for ODL in Enugu Custodial Centre affects their academic performance, 46(63%) of them agreed, 2(2.7) strongly disagreed while 6(8.2%) respondents strongly disagreed. Respondents who strongly agreed that Custodial Center environment is not conducive for learning

were 21(28%), 23(31.5%) agreed while 14(19.2%) disagreed and the remaining 15(20.5%) strongly disagreed.

The Controller NCS Enugu State during the interview processes responded that the major challenge confronting the program is lack of finance, as apart from the tuition free education given to the inmates by NOUN, no amount of money has been budgeted to run the school in the area of logistics, library service among others by Federal and State Government adding that it is only some Non-Governmental Organisations that come to their assistance when called upon to supplement the efforts of NOUN. The interviewee recommended including distance education for inmates in Government annual budgets to supplement efforts by National Open University of Nigeria in providing distance education for inmates. Another interviewee (the Desk officer) responded that apart from the assistance from NOUN, Government at all level do not finance ODL program in the Custodial Centre as there is no subvention from government across board to run the programme. He listed NGOs that have been providing assistance to include: Isaac Blessings Foundation, the Catholic Prisoners Interest Organization (CAPIO), the Catholic Institute for Justice and Peace (CIJAP), Pribola Foundation among others

Table 10: Respondents response on challenges of inadequate study facilities hindering Open and Distance Education in prisoners’ rehabilitation and reintegration at Enugu Custodial Centre.

Variables	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Does lack of internet services affect your study in Open and Distance Learning at Enugu Custodial Centre?	31 42.5%	8 10.9%	21 28.8%	13 17.8%
Does lack of relationship with your facilitators and academic advisers affect your performance?	38 52.1%	19 26%	10 13.7%	6 8.2%
Do you agree that inadequate supply of instructional materials affects your study in ODL	53 72.6%	15 20.5%	5 6.8%	0 0%
Does non-availability of Library services and stationeries affects your study in Enugu Custodial Centre student ODL	46 63%	19 26%	4 5.5%	4 5.5%
Do you agree that non posting of NOUN management staff affects your academic needs in Enugu Custodial Centre?	38 52%	16 21.9%	9 12.3%	10 13.7%

In response to whether inadequate study facilities or hinder Open and Distance Education in prisoners’ rehabilitation and reintegration at Enugu Custodial Centre, 31(42.5%) respondents

strongly agreed that lack of internet services affects their study at Enugu Custodial Centre, 8(10.9%) agreed, 21(28.8%) disagreed while 13(17.8%) strongly disagreed. Among the respondents, 38(52.1%) strongly agreed that lack of relationship with their facilitators and academic advisers affect their performance, 19(26%) respondents agreed, 10(13.7%) disagreed while 11(15%) strongly disagreed.

Those who strongly agreed that inadequate supply of instructional materials affect their study in ODL were 53(72.6%), those who agreed were 15(20.5%), while those who disagreed were 5(6.8%). None strongly disagreed. In the same vein, those who strongly agreed that non-availability of Library services and stationeries affect their study were 46(63%), 19(26%) of them agreed, 4(5.5%) disagreed while the remaining 4(5.5%) strongly disagreed. The table also shows that 38(52%) respondents strongly agreed that non-posting of NOUN management staff to Enugu Custodial Centre Special Study Centre affects their academic needs, 16(21.9%) agreed, 9(12.3%) disagreed while 10(13.8%) strongly disagreed.

Corroborating the above findings from the responses of the respondents’ that lack of relationship with their facilitators and academic advisers affect their performance, the CSS Enugu State Command responded that there are hindrances on the issue of lecturers coming to give lectures to students/inmates at the custodial centre because the Center does not have the fund to pay them Another challenge is the environment which is not very conducive for learning, it is not the best anybody can have but the student/inmates have managed due their quest to have a university education”. Another interviewee (the Deputy Desk Officer) responded that the students do not have access to internet due to the peculiar nature of prisons and again to avoid abuse. The study materials provided in hardcopy for our students are always limited in number and this make us to resort to photocopying those ones that are insufficient. The interviewee suggested that if virtual learning can be introduced, it can go a long way to help the inmates improve on their education through ODL. At least if one or two big screens can be installed in the classroom, inmates can benefit from the virtual learning.

Table 11: Personal challenges facing students of ODL in Enugu Custodian Centre

S/N	Variables	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
	The trauma and drawbacks of life in prisons is a challenge to Open and Distance Learning.	25 34.2%	26 35.6%	7 9.6%	15 20.5%
	Overcrowding of cells affects one mentally and psychologically	21 28.8%	30 41%	17 23.3%	5 6.8%
	Mixture of ODL students and non-students in one cell affects studying	49 67.1	21 28.8	3 4.1	0 0%
	Delays in trial of awaiting trial inmate	27 36.9%	26 35.7	13 17.8	7 9.6

Lack of money to take care of one's personal needs	38 52.1%	19 26%	10 13.7%	6 8.2%
Lack of communication with family and friends.	19 26%	21 28.8%	20 27.4%	13 17.8%
Poor welfare for prison inmates	39 53.4%	18 24.7%	13 17.8%	3 4.1%
Writing exams on the day of courts affects ones performance	32 43.8%	26 35.6%	12 16.4%	3 4.1%
Exploitation from staff affects my study.	13 17.8%	8 10.9%	33 45.2%	19 26%

The study found that 25 respondents (34.2%) strongly agreed that trauma and drawbacks of life in prisons are challenges in studying through Open and Distance Learning, 26(35.6%) agreed, 7(9.6%) disagreed while 15(20.5%) strongly disagreed. The table also shows that 21 respondents (28.8%) strongly agreed that overcrowding in prison Cells affect them mentally and psychologically, 30(41%) agreed, 17(23.3%) disagreed while 5 of them (6.8%) strongly disagreed. The Table further shows that 49 respondents (67.1%) strongly agreed that mixture of ODL students and non-students in one cell affects them, 21(28.8%) agreed, those who disagreed were 3(4.1%) while none strongly disagreed. Furthermore 27(36.9%) respondents responded that delays in trial of awaiting trial inmates is a challenge to studying under the Open and Distance Learning program, 26(35.7%) agreed, 13(17.8%) of them disagreed while 7(9.6%) respondents strongly disagreed. Also, 38 respondents (52.1%) strongly agreed that lack of money to take care of their personal needs is their personal challenge, 19(26%) agreed, 10(13.7%) disagreed while 6(8.2%) strongly disagreed.

In a similar manner, those who strongly agreed that lack of communication with family and friends is their personal challenge were 19(26%), those who agreed to that were 21 respondents (28.8%), 20 respondents (27.4%) disagreed while 13(17.6%) strongly disagreed. Those who strongly agreed that poor welfare for prison inmates is their personal challenge were 39(53.4%), 18(24.7%) agreed to that, 13(17.8%) disagreed while 3(4.1%) strongly disagreed. Furthermore, those who strongly agreed that writing exams on the day of courts affects their performance were 32(48.8%), 26(35.6%) respondents agreed, 12(16.4%) disagreed while 3(4.1%) strongly disagreed. The table equally showed that 13(17.8%) respondents strongly agreed that exploitation from prison staff affects their study, 8(10.9%) agreed, however, majority of them 33(45.2) in number disagreed to that while 19(26%) strongly disagreed. Furthermore the desk Officer responded that another serious challenge the Centre face in prisoner's rehabilitation and reintegration with ODL is unconducive environment for learning and this results to psychological trauma on students as there is no separate cell or hostel inside the Custodial Centre for inmates/student of ODL. The implication is that our students/ inmates are mixed up in one cell with those who are not interested in studying. Some times when our inmates/students want to read or study, there will be noise from non-students/inmates and this often cause distraction.”

Test of Hypothesis Three

Ho3: Institutional challenges, inadequate study Facilities, and Personal Challenges have significant effects on prisoners' reformation, rehabilitation, and reintegration with open and distance Education at maximum custodial centre.

Table 12: multiple regression analysis of Institutional challenges, inadequate study Facilities, and Personal Challenges on prisoners' rehabilitation and reintegration with open and distance Education.

Model	Unstandardized		Standardized t	Sig.
	Coefficients			
	B	Std. Error	Beta	
(Constant)	1.397	.142	9.807	.000
1 Institutional Challenges	-.083	.047	.100	.012
Inadequate study Facilities	-.216	.061	.200	.000
Personal Challenge	-.058	.039	-.080	.013

a. Dependent Variable: Rehabilitations reformation and reintegration

In table 3, multiple regression analysis was conducted to assess the effects of institutional challenges, inadequate study Facilities, and personal challenges on prisoners' rehabilitation and reintegration with open and distance Education. The t-test result showed that probability values of (institutional challenges, inadequate study facilities, and personal challenges) with Beta coefficient of -.83, -.216 and -.058 respectively negatively effects prisoners' rehabilitation and reintegration with open and distance Education. The associated p-values (sig.) of these exogenous variables were all less than 0.05 level of significance, an indication that these exogenous variables have negative significant effect on prisoner adaptation to open and distance learning programme at Enugu Custodian Centre. Hence, this mean that there were significant negative effects of institutional challenges, inadequate study Facilities, and personal challenges on prisoners' reformation, rehabilitation, and reintegration with open and distance Education. Therefore the alternative hypothesis is accepted.

To address all these problems/challenges the Desk Officer/Interviewee responded thus:

“The study Centre need a bus that can take us to various LGAs to solicit for assistance because it is their ward/indigenes that are in prison. They need to be informed that their son and daughters who are students here have changed since they joined NOUN ODL programs. There is need to make prisoner education through ODL and other literacy programs in prisons to be compulsory for all inmates within the school age. It is not ideal for a young and vibrant inmate to continuously stay in his or her cell for years without capacity building through education. If prisoners' education is made compulsory, those affected will have the opportunity of going to school or in the alternative, engage in other vocational skill”.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Prisoners' education is very crucial for the success of their rehabilitation, reformation and reintegration as it is the gate way to build the skills and capacity of the inmates to live a good and crime free life, integrate into the society and end recidivism. The paper has examined prisoner's

rehabilitation, and reintegration with Open and Distance Education at Enugu Maximum Correctional Centre from 2011 to 2021 and revealed the usefulness of the education program in prisoners' rehabilitation and reintegration. The paper discovered how educational and infrastructural facilities provided by National Open University of Nigeria has helped prisoners' at Enugu Custodial Centre to adapt to Open and Distance Learning program. The paper also challenges militating against the ODL program in the Custodial Centre. We therefore conclude that Prisoners education and literacy program such as ODL should be included in the nation's education curriculum and made to be compulsory for prison inmates as part of their Rehabilitation and Reintegration Program.

Based on the findings, the researcher recommends the following:

1. That the Federal Government should include prisoners' education in their annual budget so as to provide funds for the program to complement the efforts of the National Open University of Nigeria in providing education for the inmates. This will help prison inmates to get good and quality education that will help sustain them after incarceration.
2. That a separate and well equipped classroom other than normal prisoners' cell should be built at Enugu Custodial Centre with modern library facilities to help the inmates in their studies. Also the inmates should be provided with facilitators to guide them in their respective chosen course of study, and in addition, there is need for virtual learning platform to be installed in the Centre to help the students in their studies.
3. That prison inmates participating in Open and Distance Learning program should be separated from other inmates so as to provide them with a conducive environment to study. Furthermore NOUN should deploy their staff to manage ODL program in the Custodial Centre so that the inmates can be well counseled in their choice of study.

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